

Critical Review

Florian M. P. Simatupang, *Witnessing to Jesus the Spirit Baptizer: A Response to Macchia's Pentecostal Christology*

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This critical review of Florian M. P. Simatupang's article aims to identify and analyze philosophically how the author uses theological assumptions and interpretive frameworks in his arguments. This philosophical approach is important because it allows theological evaluation to go beyond the content of faith, but also to dissect the philosophical coherence of the article, including in its dialogue with Frank D. Macchia. This review uses ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological theories as a surgical tool for analysis.

The ontological assumptions underlying his argument begin to appear in the abstract section. Simatupang affirms Christ as the cosmic center, the *telos* of all things.¹ However, the reality of Christ is not understood abstractly, but rather as a transformation of the Spirit poured out upon all flesh.² Although it appears to be postpositivism, Simatupang's ontology is more accurately described as social constructivism-transformative. On the one hand, he recognizes Christ as a universal person, but on the other hand, his understanding is always mediated by social context and directed toward liberation.

This article interprets knowing (epistemology) through spiritual experience, testimony, and affection. The author emphasizes that Pentecostals know intimate and profound encounters (*'yada*) with God through their hearts.³ The author's argument aligns with social constructivism, where meaning is constructed through collective interaction and experience.

His writing clearly demonstrates his axiology, which is his commitment to solidarity and justice. Simatupang criticizes the understanding of power that legitimizes superiority, colonialism, and racism.⁴ On the contrary, faithful witness is understood as participation in

¹ Florian M.P. Simatupang, "Witnessing to Jesus the Spirit Baptizer: A Response to Macchia's Pentecostal Christology," *Pneuma* 45, nos. 3–4 (December 2023): 410, <https://doi.org/10.1163/15700747-bja10099>.

² Simatupang, "Witnessing to Jesus the Spirit Baptizer," 411.

³ Simatupang, "Witnessing to Jesus the Spirit Baptizer," 419–20.

⁴ Simatupang, "Witnessing to Jesus the Spirit Baptizer," 411, 424.

the death and resurrection of Christ.⁵ The values of solidarity and commitment to the oppressed clearly indicate a transformative interpretive framework.

Then, from a methodological perspective, Simatupang responds to Macchia in two ways: First, by engaging in critical dialogue with Macchia; Second, by offering his analytical findings to complement Macchia's argument.⁶ He emphasizes that this dialogue is open and temporary because theology must always be responsive to new contexts. Therefore, his methodology is reflective, dialogical, and open to revision, which is characteristic of the social constructivism and transformative framework. Overall, Simatupang's article highlights a combination of the interpretive frameworks of social constructivism and transformative. Transformative constructivism is evident in the critique of colonialism, while social constructivism is evident in the emphasis on experience and communal dialogue.

In their dialogue, Simatupang and Macchia both affirm Christ as the universal Baptizer of the Spirit for all people.⁷ Both agree ontologically in this regard. However, Macchia emphasizes continuity with the dogmatic tradition of the church (e.g., Nicea, Chalcedon) as a form of witness to the Spirit.⁸ In contrast, Simatupang highlights the Indonesian context, rejects colonialism, and emphasizes witness as solidarity with the oppressed.

Macchia emphasizes dogmatic tradition and cosmic unity, while Simatupang highlights affective experience, criticism of colonialism, and liberating contextual dialogue. I argue that they differ in epistemology, axiology, and methodology. Therefore, Simatupang's writing constructively expands Macchia's vision to be more contextual and partisan.

The strength of this article lies in the consistency of its philosophical assumptions, which reflect the distinctive characteristics of social constructivism—transformative frameworks—and its boldness in connecting Christology with social criticism. However, the weakness of the article is that Simatupang uses Colossians 1:17 only normatively without in-depth exegesis. Two things that could be considered in developing this paper, for example, in further research, are expanding the theological dialogue with other Pentecostal theologians in Indonesia and strengthening the exegetical basis to support the critique of colonialism.

⁵ Simatupang, "Witnessing to Jesus the Spirit Baptizer," 418.

⁶ Simatupang, "Witnessing to Jesus the Spirit Baptizer," 412.

⁷ See Frank D. Macchia, "Jesus the Spirit Baptizer: Toward a Pentecostal Christology," *Pneuma* 45, nos. 3–4 (December 2023): 393, <https://doi.org/10.1163/15700747-bja10100>.

⁸ Macchia, "Jesus the Spirit Baptizer," 394–96.

Overall, this article's interpretive framework focuses on criticism of colonialism, racism, and partiality toward oppressed groups. Although he agrees with Macchia on Pentecostal Christology in his dialogue, Simatupang goes further with his critique of colonialism and contextual offerings. Thus, this critical review emphasizes the importance of philosophical categories in assessing theological works, as they reveal the coherence and tensions that shape the direction of contemporary theological development.

References

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